

A Comparison of Tomographic SAR Reconstruction Methods Using Spaceborne Data

Prithvi Laguduvan Thyagarajan, Holger Nies, Florian Behner, Simon Reuter, Otmar Loffeld

Center for Sensor Systems (ZESS), University of Siegen, Germany
 {laguduvan.thyagarajan, nies, behner, reuter, loffeld}@zess.uni-siegen.de

Abstract—The paper focuses on the application of SAR tomographic inversion using compressive sensing (CS) as well as traditional methods in the use of spaceborne data. In contrast to prior art approaches applied to satellite data, novel CS reconstruction approaches, that combine sparse with prior information, are explored and analyzed. First results using data from the German TerraSAR-X satellite will be presented.

Keywords—synthetic aperture radar, tomographic SAR, reconstruction algorithms, compressive sensing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Synthetic Aperture Radar has established itself as an advanced method in the field of remote sensing. It allows Earth's surface to be mapped from a moving platform such as an airplane or satellite. A SAR system has advantages over other remote sensing systems for its ability to image the ground irrespective of the weather conditions, day or night and also offer potential information such as polarimetric and scattering data of a target. The imaging geometry of SAR is hereby different to the optical geometry, as the imaging plane is rather spanned by azimuth and range instead of azimuth and elevation. Hence a single SAR image projects a three dimensional scene onto a two dimensional plane. To retrieve the real three dimensional (3-D) localization and motion of scattering objects, advanced interferometric methods, like persistent scatterer interferometry (PSI) or SAR tomography, are required, which exploit stacks of complex-valued SAR images with diversity in space and time [1]. The recent advances of the space technology involving constellations of satellites, and the planning for future missions involving formation of satellites, have the ability to acquire simultaneous (multi-baseline) SAR images repeatedly over the time. This, in turn, has pushed the research and development of new techniques capable of processing, jointly and coherently, the stacks of SAR images. SAR tomography (TomoSAR) is a technique that allows resolving scatterer densities in the third native radar co-ordinate "elevation (s)" by exploiting its ability to acquire multipass acquisitions at different orbital positions to form a virtual array [2]. TomoSAR is a major contributor to monitor and explore solutions for urban area developments as they play an important role in tackling the global climate change. Over the last two decades SAR Tomography and differential SAR Tomography has been extensively researched [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9].

Many imaging techniques have been invented which can provide high resolution 3-D mapping and reconstruction

of an urban area. However, some of the requirements for urban monitoring are maintaining the meter azimuth-range resolution, improving the elevation resolution, achieving high 3-D localization accuracy even in the presence of unmodeled non-Gaussian noise and retrieving nonlinear motion [1].

Taking the requirements into consideration, this paper explores the different methods involved in the reconstruction of Tomographic SAR spaceborne data.

II. TOMOSAR IMAGING MODEL

The TomoSAR data stacks are formed by multipass acquisitions of an area of interest at different times and across different orbital positions.

The Fig.1 depicts the geometry of TomoSAR for different positions $P_n \forall n \in [1, N]$ with L_x as the cross-range aperture and ϑ being the look angle. Height profile of the scatterers fall in the same range-azimuth resolution cell for a single path. The range resolution ρ_r depends on the system bandwidth B and the azimuth resolution ρ_z depends on the length of the synthetic aperture L_x .

Fig. 1. TomoSAR geometry

The signal at a fixed azimuth and range pixel at a generic n^{th} antenna is given by:

$$h_n = \int_{\Delta s} \gamma(s) \exp\left(-j \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} r_n(s)\right) ds \quad (1)$$

where, $\gamma(s)$ is the reflected signal along elevation s , $r_n(s)$ is the distance of the scatterer from the n^{th} antenna at elevation s . The distance at elevation point O , $r_n(0)$, is subtracted from data at each antenna, $r_n(s) - r_n(0)$. Therefore, the data processed via deramping is given by the focused complex value,

$$g_n = h_n \exp\left(j \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} r_n(s)\right) = \int_{\Delta s} \gamma(s) \exp(-j 2\pi \xi_n s) ds \quad (2)$$

where, ξ_n is the spatial frequency in elevation given by,

$$\xi_n = -\frac{2b_n}{\lambda r}. \quad (3)$$

The imaging model can be formulated as with the noise parameter, ϵ is given as,

$$g = \mathbf{R}\gamma + \epsilon \quad (4)$$

where, $g = [g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n]^T$, \mathbf{R} is a $N \times L$ matrix given as $R_{nl} = \exp(-j2\pi\xi_n s_l)$, γ is a discrete reflectivity vector for L elements, $s_l \forall l \in [1, L]$ is the discrete elevation positions. s profiles for every $x - r$ pixel can be obtained by SAR tomographic processing of the data stacks. Reconstruction of these s profiles is the spectrum estimation problem and valid scatterers can be obtained from the focused reflectivity function of the model.

III. OVERVIEW OF EXISTING ALGORITHMS

Based on the standard linear equations for tomographic SAR system, as given in Eq.(4), the reconstruction of the s profile can be given as the inversion of the system. The inversion must be carefully implemented because: (i) the Fourier samples are irregularly spaced at ξ_n , (ii) their number N may be small, (iii) the SNR may be low for the majority of the pixels, (iv) the data may contain non-Gaussian phase noise due to uncompensated atmospheric delay and unmodeled motion and (v) the orbit tube of modern SAR satellites is tight leading to a low elevation resolution [2].

There are many reconstruction techniques and the most relevant ones are beamforming, Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), Capon, MUSIC, Nonlinear Least Squares and SImmer.

A. Beamforming

Beamforming in TomoSAR can be expressed as an array signal processing problem and was initially used for solving layover effects in TomoSAR [10], [11]. Based on the imaging model given by Eq.(4), the reflectivity along the elevation direction can be formulated as,

$$\hat{\gamma} = \mathbf{R}^H g \quad (5)$$

The estimate of the reflected power in the elevation direction for every elevation position is given as,

$$|\hat{\gamma}|^2 = |r_L^H g|^2 \quad (6)$$

Conventional beamforming is very efficient but has no super resolution capability and also has a severe sidelobe problem caused due to irregular sampling [10].

B. Singular Value Decomposition (SVD)

Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) can be used for reconstruction of the reflectivity of the signal through the pseudo inverse of \mathbf{R} . The SVD of \mathbf{R} can be given as

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{V}^H = \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbf{u}_n \sigma_n \mathbf{v}_n^T \quad (7)$$

where, the orthonormal columns are given by $\mathbf{U} = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_N)$ and $\mathbf{V} = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_N)$, $\sigma = \text{diag}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_N)$ is the diagonal matrix consisting of singular values that are positive real numbers such that, $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \sigma_N = 0$. Based on Eq.(7), the reflected power is obtained by

$$\hat{\gamma} = \mathbf{R}^\dagger g = \sum_{n=1}^N \sigma_n^{-1} (\mathbf{u}_n^T g) \mathbf{v}_n \quad (8)$$

SVD is chosen for tomographic processing because of its good performance at high noise levels without compromising the spatial resolution in the azimuth-slant range plane [12].

C. Adaptive Beamforming (Capon)

Adaptive beamforming or Capon, when compared to traditional beamforming method, introduces self interference cancellation by weighting the steering vectors according to the covariance matrix, $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{gg}$ [10]. The covariance matrix is given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{gg} = \frac{1}{N_L} \sum_{m=1}^{N_L} (\mathbf{g}_m \mathbf{g}_m^H) \quad (9)$$

where, N_L is the number of multi-looking measurements, g_m is the measurement vector for every m^{th} look. Then, the reflected power for each elevation position, s_l is given as,

$$|\hat{\gamma}_l|_{CAPON}^2 = \frac{1}{\mathbf{r}_l^H \hat{\mathbf{C}}_{gg}^{-1} \mathbf{r}_l} \quad (10)$$

The performance of Capon is better in terms of elevation resolution and sidelobe suppression, but can lead to phase errors due to its unmodelled motion and small looks [10].

D. Multiple Signal Classification (MUSIC)

Another prominent model based spectral estimation method is the Multiple Signal Classification (MUSIC). The covariance matrix $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{gg}$ is separated into eigenvalues and eigenvectors. The K number of scatterers can be estimated from the eigenvalues or can be given a priori. $N - K$ eigenvectors determine the noise subspace, $\hat{\mathbf{G}}$. Hence, the spectrum at each elevation position, s_l is given as

$$|\hat{\gamma}_l|_{MUSIC}^2 = \frac{1}{\mathbf{r}_l^H \hat{\mathbf{G}} \hat{\mathbf{G}}^H \mathbf{r}_l} \quad (11)$$

MUSIC offers better resolution and sidelobe suppression in comparison to beamforming and Capon [10]. It should also be noted that the performance of MUSIC is good for uncorrelated signals but the estimation precision deteriorates when the signals are highly correlated [13].

E. Nonlinear Least Squares

The next best estimator of reflectivity is the Nonlinear least squares (NLS). With reference to the imaging model presented in Eq.(4), K scatterers with elevations of $s = [s_1, \dots, s_K]$ is assumed and the imaging model reduces to,

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{s})\gamma(\mathbf{s}) + \epsilon \quad (12)$$

where, $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{s})$ is the the $N \times K$ matrix with $R_{nk} = \exp(-j2\pi\xi_n s_k)$. The above equation is nonlinear in elevation but linear in amplitude and the least squares estimate is minimized for a given reflectivity and the optimum estimate is given by:

$$\hat{\gamma}(\hat{s}) = \arg \min_{\gamma(s)} \|\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{R}(s)\gamma(s)\|_2^2 \quad (13)$$

Due to the large computational effort to the multi-dimensional search, non linear least squares is not recommended for practical data processing [10].

F. SLIMMER

A CS-based TomoSAR algorithm known as Scale-down by L1 norm Minimization, Model selection and Estimation Reconstruction (SLIMMER), is a spectral estimation algorithm and was first demonstrated by [10]. The algorithm explores sparsity in the elevation direction. The algorithm can be divided into 3 main parts: 1) a dimensionality scale down by L_1 norm minimization, 2) model selection and 3) linear parameter estimation. Assuming that the elevation profile is sparse, there can be infinite number of solutions for such a system and the sparsest and most probable outcome is given by the L_0 norm of the reflectivity vector. Since the problem is NP-hard, the L_0 norm is replaced by the L_1 norm. Since the raw data measurement is noisy, the L_1 norm is minimized with a residual data term.

$$\hat{\gamma} = \arg \min_{\gamma} \|\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{R}\gamma\|_2^2 + \lambda_k \|\gamma\|_1 \quad (14)$$

The sparsest estimate of reflectivity can be given by the Eq.(14) given that the matrix R satisfies the two main properties of compressive sensing: Restricted Isometry Property (RIP) and Incoherence [14]. Nevertheless, these properties are not completely satisfied in TomoSAR for several reasons such the matrix R is not optimum and is predetermined by the measurement system and oversampling of the elevation points can make R overcomplete. However, the step of dimensionality scale down by L_1 norm minimization can shrink R and give the sparsest estimate of γ which may contain outliers.

The second step of SLIMMER is the model order selection which removes the estimate of γ of insignificant, spurious scatterers and gives an estimate of the number of scatterers, \hat{K} in the elevation profile. Assuming $\theta(K)$ as the unknown phases, amplitudes and elevation of each of the scatterers, the best model fit can be given by the likelihood as: $p(g|\hat{\theta}(K), K)$. The likelihood criteria is then given by:

$$\hat{K} = \arg \min_K \left\{ -2 \ln p(g|\hat{\theta}(K), K) + 2C(K) \right\} \quad (15)$$

where, $C(K)$ is the complexity penalty and is proportional to the number of scatterers, K , i.e., $C(k) \propto \|\gamma\|_0$. Eq.(15) is a $L_2 - L_0$ norm minimization problem with a few known K candidate elevation positions.

The final step in the algorithm is the is the linear parameter estimation where $\mathbf{R}(\hat{s})$ is the $N \times \hat{K}$ mapping matrix with $R_{n,k}(\hat{s}) = \exp(-j2\pi\xi_n \hat{s}_k)$. \hat{s}_k is the estimated elevation value of k^{th} scatterer. The final estimate of reflectivity is obtained by solving the following linear system of equation:

$$g = \mathbf{R}(\hat{s})\gamma(\hat{s}) + v' \quad (16)$$

where v' involves the model error and measurement noise. Hence, the estimate of complex valued reflectivity is given by the following least squares solution

$$\hat{\gamma}(\hat{s}) = (\mathbf{R}(\hat{s})^H \mathbf{R}(\hat{s}))^{-1} \mathbf{R}(\hat{s})^H g \quad (17)$$

The final step is performed as the $L_2 - L_1$ norm minimization tends to underestimate the value of γ . Since amplitude fidelity is not the main purpose of TomoSAR makes the SLIMMER an unbiased CS algorithm [1][10].

IV. FIRST RESULTS USING SPACEBORNE DATA

The main goal of our project is to compare and optimize different methods for reconstructing tomographic SAR data. For verification purposes, we intend to check the robustness of the methods using both, airborne and spaceborne data sets.

A. Geometry and data analysis

The scene we want to use for our investigations is the city center of cologne including different types of buildings and infrastructure shown in Fig.2. The data come from TerraSAR-X, which covered the area in a high number of repetitions within a period from 08/05/2012 to 12/10/2014 in High Resolution Spotlight (HS) mode using an operating bandwidth of 300 MHz at a center frequency of 9.65 GHz.

Fig. 2. Cut out from the scene to be examined (Cologne city center, image©DLR 2014).

Since the satellite orbit is kept in a tube of 250 m (standard deviation) in relation to a reference orbit [15], a different

Fig. 3. Block diagram for TomoSAR data reconstruction.

across-track angle is available for each acquisition, which enables SAR interferometry and SAR tomography. A data set of 40 processed SAR images is available for our investigations.

B. Data preprocessing

A main task for the use of the data for SAR tomography is the careful generation of co-registered data stacks, which is actually the first task in the tomographic SAR reconstruction (see Fig. 3). The slave images are resampled to the geometry of one master image; the quality check is done by analyzing interferometric pairs. The registration is based on the accurate orbit and time information from TerraSAR-X as well as on digital elevation models that we receive from Geobasis NRW.

The collection of the data to be used for height imaging was obtained using repeated passes at a long period of time. This fact introduces additional calibration issues related to decorrelation, atmospheric phase delay (APD) variation and deformations (also slowly), which will be corrected in the phase calibration block. After subsequent amplitude adjustment of the individual images, we receive a calibrated data stack that is used for further tomographic SAR processing.

V. OUTLOOK AND CONCLUSION

In the final paper more details of the experimental part are given including results of reconstruction and a comparison of the competing algorithms using the data which is mentioned in the manuscript. This comparison includes the computation time, robustness and verification of the height results using groundtruth data.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 860370.

The authors would like to sincerely thank the TerraSAR-X Science team for providing the data for our analysis.

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Zhu and R. Bamler, "Superresolving SAR tomography for multidimensional imaging of urban areas: Compressive sensing-based TomoSAR inversion," *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Newsletter*, vol. 31, pp. 51–58, 2014.
- [2] G.Fornaro, A. Pauciullo, D. Reale, X. Zhu, and R. Bamler, "SAR tomography: an advanced tool for spaceborne 4d radar scanning with application to imaging and monitoring of cities and single buildings," *IEEE Signal Process. Mag. (IEEE Signal Processing Magazine)*, pp. 9–17, 2012.
- [3] G.Fornaro, F. Lombardini, and F. Serafino, "Three-dimensional multipass sar focusing: experiments with long-term spaceborne data," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing (IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing)*, vol. 43, pp. 702–714, 2005.
- [4] X. Zhu and R. Bamler, "Very high resolution spaceborne SAR tomography in urban environment," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing (IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing)*, vol. 48, p. 4296–4308, 2010.
- [5] G.Fornaro, D.Reale, and F.Serafino, "Four-dimensional SAR imaging for height estimation and monitoring of single and double scatterers," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing (IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing)*, vol. 47, p. 224–237, 2009.
- [6] F. Gini, F.Lombardini, and M. Montanari, "Layover solution in multibaseline SAR interferometry," *IEEE Trans. Aerosp. Electron. Syst. (IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems)*, vol. 38, p. 1344–1356, 2002.
- [7] G. Nan, R. G. Fernando, Y. Wang, Y. Shi, and X. X. Zhu, "Spaceborne staring spotlight SAR tomography—a first demonstration with terraSAR-x," *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Appl. Earth Observations Remote Sensing (IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing)*, vol. 11, p. 3743–3756, 2018.
- [8] F. Lombardini, "Differential tomography: a new framework for SAR interferometry," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing (IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing)*, vol. 43, p. 37–44, 2005.
- [9] A.Reigber and A. Moreira, "First demonstration of airborne SAR tomography using multibaseline l-band data," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing (IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing)*, vol. 38, p. 2142–2152, 2000.
- [10] X. Zhu, "Very high resolution tomographic SAR inversion for urban infrastructure monitoring —a sparse and nonlinear tour," *PhD. thesis, Deutsche Geodätische Kommission, Reihe C, Nr.666, Verlag der Bayerischen Akademie der Wissenschaften*, 2011.
- [11] P.Pasquali, C. Prati, F. Rocca, and M. Seymour, "A 3-d experiment with esml data," *International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium(IGARSS)*, 1995.
- [12] L. Wei, T. Balz, M. Liao, and L. Zhang, "TerraSAR-X stripmap data interpretation of complex urban scenarios with 3d SAR tomography," *Journal of Sensors*, vol. 2014, 2014.
- [13] P. Stoica and A. Nehorai, "Music, maximum likelihood, and cramer-rao bound," *IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, vol. 37, 1989.
- [14] R. Baraniuk, "Compressive sensing," *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 24, pp. 118–126, 2007.
- [15] M. Eineder, N. Adam, R. Bamler, N. Yague-Martinez, and H. Breit, "Spaceborne Spotlight SAR Interferometry with TerraSAR-X," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 47, no. 5, pp. 1524–1535, 2009.